

Tracing people living with HIV who have been lost to follow-up in countries of Eastern Europe and Central Asia: Results and lessons learned

Roman Yorick, Jake Rashbass
Elton John AIDS Foundation

Background

The Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA) region has been falling behind the global achievements in the test and treat strategy. In 2022, there were an estimated 2 million people living with HIV in EECA. Of the 1.24 million (62%) PLHIV who know their status, 220,000 (18%) are not on ART and considered lost to follow-up (LTFU). Although this percentage has been reduced from 51% in 2015, it is still significantly higher than the global percentage of LTFU (11%).¹

In 2020, to respond to these and other challenges in the EECA region, the Elton John AIDS Foundation (the Foundation) in partnership with Gilead Sciences Europe launched a groundbreaking five-year (2020-2025) \$25M RADIAN initiative. RADIAN grants support local

community-based projects in 25 EECA countries addressing the needs of key populations (KP), including people who use drugs, men who have sex with men, transgender people, sex workers, migrants, and people in prisons, as well as PLHIV and sexual partners of KPs and PLHIV. Grants are assessed and administered by the Foundation. Gilead has no involvement in the selection and assessment of award applicants and winners.

The Foundation has become the largest non-corporate philanthropic HIV donor in the EECA region.² In 2020-2024, the Foundation supported 43 projects by 31 non-government organizations across 14 countries to meaningfully address new HIV infections and deaths from AIDS related illnesses in EECA.

Interventions

Since 2020, under the RADIAN program, the Foundation has supported 13 community-based initiatives across 8 countries in the EECA region that included LTFU identification, tracing and return to ART as part of their project activities.

PLHIV lost to follow-up have been defined as people who missed their ART pick-up appointment at the HIV clinic (AIDS Center) for 28 days or more. These also include people who tested positive for HIV but did not start ART for over 28 days. PLHIV LTFU were further divided into:

- **Recent LTFU** – between 28 days and 12 months; and
- **Long LTFU** – over 12 months.

Project activities included:

- **Compiling lists of PLHIV LTFU** by medical staff of HIV clinics (AIDS Centers), including the latest available contact information, such as residence address and mobile number;
- **Contacting PLHIV LTFU** or their trusted contacts on the phone, if reachable;
- Making **home visits** by peer counselors together with HIV clinic staff to PLHIV who can't be reached by phone, or who do not agree to come to the clinic to re-initiate on ART;
- Conducting **peer outreach** to key population communities with **HIV testing services**

where PLHIV who know their status but do not receive ART have been identified; and

- Providing **motivational counseling, psychosocial support and peer navigation services** to return LTFU PLHIV to care and (re-)initiate them on ART.

Results

As a result, community-based organizations in partnership with HIV clinic staff:

- **Traced almost 49,200 PLHIV LTFU**, or 22.4% of the total LTFU in EECA;
- **Contacted 24,047 PLHIV LTFU**, which is 10.9% of all LTFU in EECA, and 48.8% of those traced; and
- **(Re-)initiated on ART 18,830 LTFU**, or 8.6% of the total LTFU in EECA, and 89.3% of those contacted.

Lessons learned

- In all project locations, joint efforts between community-based peer counsellors and HIV clinic staff were **the first such experience tracing PLHIV LTFU**. In many locations, standard operating procedures were developed and institutionalised that will last beyond the lifetime of individual projects.
- **To meet the legal requirement of confidentiality** of the HIV status: (a) peer counsellors can be hired as HIV clinic staff; (b) PLHIV when they are initially registered with the HIV clinic (AIDS Center) are requested to sign a consent of referral to a peer counsellor; (c) initial contact with LTFU is established by a health worker who then refers PLHIV to a peer counsellor; or (d) the health facility signs agreements with the NGO or its staff that include strict non-disclosure clauses.
- Tracing recent LTFU requires much less time and effort and has a much higher success rate than tracing long LTFU. This means **early identification and tracing of LTFU** is of the utmost importance.
- Incorrect information on ART indications both among health providers (still initiating ART based on the CD4 counts) and PLHIV alike (not feeling sick) is one of the major reasons for PLHIV dropping out of care. **Provider and patient education** is a powerful tool in preventing PLHIV loss to follow-up care.
- HIV care in EECA still highly centralised in specialised clinics (AIDS Centers and infectious disease offices) results in barriers to access, such as travel time and distance, transportation costs and inconvenient office hours. **HIV care provided at primary level** is the optimal solution to this problem.
- Self-stigma preventing PLHIV from accessing HIV services is much more prevalent among PLHIV (67%) than stigma experienced from health providers (22%). **Interventions addressing mental health of PLHIV**, including self-stigma, are important in bringing LTFU back to care and improving retention.
- A high rate of burn out and staff turnover is seen among peer counsellors working with PLHIV LTFU. Many of the peers have recently experienced the same challenges they are seeing in their beneficiaries. Without professional training in social work, they are not able to set boundaries with clients. **Professional supervision and other mental health services** are essential for maintaining NGO staff working with LTFU.

Voices from the field

This was our first experience of such joint interaction, joint work with the AIDS Center. We were pioneers in this project. We learned how to talk to clients and how not to disclose information.

We created an algorithm for field trips for further work together with the AIDS Center staff: after how many days are they transferred to the field trip, what to say, etc. The algorithm includes the most practical recommendations on how and what you can say, how to talk with neighbors, what you can't say, what to do if the apartment is sealed

The main difficulty is to find a patient whose patient record contains an address where the person does not live and no telephone number. Neighbors play a big role here. At the reception, receptionists record the actual address from words, and not from an ID; not everyone asks for a phone number. If a person rented an apartment and then moved, it is difficult to find him

I have been sick for 15 years now, and I felt fine. I knew the information about treatment, but did not plan to take it, and everything was fine. My ex-wife is also positive, and she really felt bad. I told her, go get treatment, but she doesn't care. Now I don't know how she is. I couldn't convince her because I didn't take the treatment myself and felt fine. And I did not meet the right specialist earlier

The most difficult thing is traveling to the AIDS Center, for me it is far away. It's difficult without your own transport; it's a long way to get by bus or taxi. The remoteness of the infectious disease office from the village is a big problem. It's poor there. Paying for travel helps. There is no home delivery of ART yet. People were reimbursed for their travel, which is a big help. For people who use drugs, spending on travel is not a priority.

Our city is small, everyone knows each other, no one wants to open up, so it's difficult to gather people for a support group. Although I am a consultant and many people know me, I will never reveal my HIV status to strangers or at work. I can even get a certificate that I am negative if necessary at work. Sometimes you meet a positive acquaintance, for example, he also brought a child to afterschool activities, we silently catch each other's eyes and somehow it's scary that he knows that suddenly the parents would find out, although our children are negative

It was difficult, I passed the information through myself, it was emotionally difficult, I was worried and wanted to quit. When there is negativity from clients. It's good that a psychologist worked with us. The project helped me learn how to get things done

I myself am sick, I use substances, and it's very difficult, I sometimes want to quit everything. But work on the project held me back several times. I could always talk to psychologists, and the manager supported me and didn't let me down.

Conclusions

- RADIAN partners have **documented and costed the models of LTFU tracing** and (re-)initiating on ART. Immediate next steps are for **governments to assume these costs and functions** to reach the "third 95" in the EECA region.
- RADIAN shows that **effective foreign-funded community-led HIV services** for KPs in challenging EECA environments are possible, if programs intentionally earn communities' trust, optimize service modalities, and bake in sustainability approaches.
- With the HIV epidemic growing in EECA and limited domestic resources allocated to KPs, **expanded international donor support** is urgently needed.

References

1. UNAIDS Data 2023. https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2023/2023_unaids_data (Accessed July 11, 2024)
2. Funders Concerned About AIDS. Philanthropic Support to Address HIV and AIDS in 2021. October 2023. <https://resourcetracking.fcaids.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/FCAA-SupportReport2021.pdf> (Accessed July 11, 2024)

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